

Impact of AI-Driven Learning on Undergraduate Mathematics Students' Motivation, Persistence, and Academic Performance in Universities, Kano State

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This study examines the impact of AI-driven learning on undergraduate mathematics students' motivation, persistence, and academic performance. Three hypotheses were developed and tested. This study used a quasi-experimental design with pre- and post-test measurements. The population consisted of Level 200 students with two intact classes, making 108 students the sample size (56 experimental, 52 control). Three instruments were utilized; the Undergraduate Mathematics Persistence Scale (UMPS), the Undergraduate Mathematics Motivation Scale (UMMS), and the Mathematics Performance Test (MPT). These instruments demonstrated validity with reliability coefficients of 0.83, 0.86, and 0.78, respectively. Data analysis included means, standard deviations, independent t-tests, and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. The findings reveal that AI-driven learning significantly enhanced motivation (pre-test: $M = 3.49$, $SD = 0.11$; post-test: $M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.23$; $Z = -6.518$, $p < 0.001$, $r = 0.87$) and persistence (pre-test: $M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.28$; post-test: $M = 4.40$, $SD = 0.30$; $Z = -6.524$, $p < 0.001$, $r = 0.87$) among undergraduate mathematics students. Academic performance also showed significant improvement, with experimental group students ($M = 80.44$, $SD = 5.91$) outperforming control group students ($M = 71.81$, $SD = 6.12$; $t(106) = 7.455$, $p = 0.001$, $r = 1.44$). This study recommends that university lecturers incorporate AI-driven learning into mathematics instruction to enhance student outcomes.

Keywords:
AI-driven learning, Motivation, Persistence, Academic Performance, Mathematics

Introduction

The development of science, technology, and many other fields of human endeavour relies on the fundamental discipline of mathematics. Mathematics can be described as the study of quantity, structure, space, and change using thorough logical reasoning and symbolic representation to identify and analyse patterns and relationships. Mathematics is a way of thinking that encourages abstraction, generalisation, and problem-solving skills beyond calculation (Gray & Berggren, 2025; Kamid et al., 2022; Laurent et al., 2022). Mathematics plays an essential and broad role in today's world. In the physical sciences, it helps

to articulate the laws of nature and predict outcomes through mathematical models. In engineering and technology, mathematics drives innovation by optimizing processes and designing systems. In social sciences and humanities, it supports data analysis, economic forecasting, and decision-making. Despite the importance of mathematics and its applications across various fields, undergraduate students often face significant challenges in achieving academic success in this area (Betiang et al., 2025; Hernandez-Martinez, et al, 2024; Rezvanifard & Radmehr, 2024).

Academic performance in mathematics reflects the degree to which students acquire

and demonstrate mathematical knowledge, skills, and competencies through formal assessment. It is shaped by both cognitive and affective factors, including students' motivation, such as mastery, performance, and avoidance goals, and their persistence in overcoming academic difficulties. Additionally, external impacts, such as learning environments and instructional methods, can significantly impact outcomes (Zheng & Mustapha, 2022; Suleiman, 2023; Chazan et al., 2021). The development of learning platforms empowered by artificial intelligence (AI) offers new potential to improve student engagement and motivation, remain persistent, and personalize learning according to each student's needs. Enhancing methods for instruction and encouraging academic performance require an understanding of how these tools impact undergraduate students' learning experiences and mathematical performance.

Statement of Problem

Teaching mathematics is challenging at all levels of education. In some cases, it is even more difficult at tertiary institutions because of its abstract nature. Several studies have been conducted to simplify teaching and learning of this complex subject. With advancements in computer technology, particularly artificial intelligence (AI), many aspects of human life have become easier, including education. Trends in mathematics education focus on integrating AI into teaching and learning mathematics, with the belief that AI will have a significant impact. Therefore, this study examined the impact of AI-driven learning on students' motivation, persistence, and academic performance in undergraduate mathematics.

Research Objectives

The following objectives guided the study

1. To investigate the impact of AI-driven learning on the motivation of undergraduate mathematics students.
2. To examine the impact of AI-driven learning on the persistence of undergraduate mathematics students.
3. To determine the difference in the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students between those using AI-driven learning and those employing lecture methods?

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of AI-driven learning on the motivation of undergraduate mathematics students?
2. What is the impact of AI-driven learning on the persistence of undergraduate mathematics students?
3. Is there any difference in the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students between those using AI-driven learning and those employing lecture methods?

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: AI-driven learning has no significant impact on the motivation of undergraduate mathematics students.

H₀₂: AI-driven learning has no significant impact on the persistence of undergraduate mathematics students.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students between those taught using AI-driven learning and those employing lecture methods.

Literature Review

This study is based on Ryan and Deci (2019) Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which posits that motivation arises from three fundamental psychological needs which are autonomy, competence and relatedness. These

needs are met in the context of AI-driven learning through collaborative AI environments that encourage social interaction, adjustable difficulty level to fit students' skills (competence), and personalized learning path (autonomy). The study also make Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, specifically the idea of self-efficacy, which contends that students' motivation and persistence are influenced by their opinion of their own capacity to complete academic task (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020).

AI-driven Learning and Motivation in Mathematics

Artificial Intelligence has emerged as a transformative force in education, offering new possibilities for encouraging student involvement and motivation in mathematics learning. AI is the ability of machines to process large amounts of data and modify their answers over time to carry out cognitive tasks that are typically associated with human intelligence, including learning, reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making (Kundu, 2024). In mathematics education, AI systems are designed to replicate human-like teaching approaches, providing students with personalized instruction that considers their unique learning styles, abilities, and weaknesses (Mohamed et al., 2022; Rizvi, 2023).

Motivation, an essential aspect of assessing academic success, involves the inner processes that drive, guide, and sustain students' learning endeavors (Ryan & Vansteenkiste, 2023; Reeve, 2024). Motivation affects students' readiness to tackle difficult ideas, persist through problem-solving tasks, and use effective learning techniques in the context of mathematics. AI-driven learning environments, through adaptive content delivery, instant feedback,

and gamified learning experiences, have the potential to enhance motivation, both within and outside (Rizvi, 2023).

One of the most notable applications of AI is the Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS), which imitates a teacher's adaptive instructional approach, tailoring explanations, practice tasks, and feedback to each learner's needs (Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024). The ability of these systems to dynamically modify the difficulty of problems, offer different approaches to solving them, and offer prompt corrections has been associated with increased learner interest, confidence, and self-efficacy in mathematics (Mohamed et al., 2022). By providing interactive problem-solving assistance, detailed explanations, and visual representations that make abstract mathematical concepts easier to understand, AI-driven learning tools such as Photomath, Mathway, Symbolab, Microsoft Math Solver, Gauth, and MathGPTPro also help boost motivation (Salleh et al., 2025). AI systems support sustained motivation by incorporating elements such as progress tracking, performance dashboards, and performance badges (Rizvi, 2023). These features promote self-awareness of learning progress and enhance students' sense of accomplishment, encouraging them to persist in tackling complex mathematical problems. Furthermore, one of the most widely used AI methods in mathematics education is robotics, which has been designed to engage students through interactive, hands-on activities that relate abstract concepts to real-world applications (Zhong & Xia, 2020; Seckel et al., 2021).

According to review of the existing literature, AI-driven learning environments significantly increase student motivation through a variety of methods. These include gamified experiences that make abstract topics

more approachable and interesting, rapid feedback that reduces frustration and encourages self-correction, and adaptive content delivery that adjusts to each learner's personal pace. By imitating a teacher's adaptive teaching style and offering customized explanations, practice exercises, and feedback depending on each learner's individual requirements, Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) are good examples of these motivational processes (Opesemowo & Ndlovu, 2024).

AI-driven tools such as Photomath, Mathway, Symbolab, Microsoft Math Solver, Gauth, and MathGPTPro provide interactive problem-solving assistance, detailed explanations, and visual representations that make abstract mathematical concepts more accessible (Salleh et al., 2025). While these tools demonstrate significant potential in supporting learners, some scholars caution that they may unintentionally reduce students' tolerance for productive struggle, which is critical for developing deep conceptual understanding and problem-solving resilience. Furthermore, although evidence highlights their effectiveness in enhancing motivation and engagement, important research gaps remain. In particular, questions persist regarding the long-term sustainability of AI-enhanced motivation and whether students can maintain consistent engagement and self-directed learning once AI support is reduced or withdrawn. Addressing these concerns calls for longitudinal research to evaluate the durability of motivational and learning benefits associated with AI-based tools.

AI-driven Learning and Persistence

Persistence in learning refers to the sustained effort and determination students exhibit when engaging in academic tasks, particularly in the face of difficulties or

setbacks (Daza-Pérez et al., 2024; Feng & Papi, 2020). Persistence matters in mathematics because it allows students to explore several solution approaches, solve problems in multiple steps, and obtain deeper conceptual understanding (DiNapoli, 2023).

In the context of higher education, persistence is often undermined by large class sizes, inconsistent instructional support, limited learning resources, and delayed feedback (Jacob et al., 2023). These challenges can lead to disengagement, particularly in mathematically intensive fields. AI-driven learning environments offer an effective strategy to address these limitations by creating adaptive, interactive, and learner-centered instructional experiences that respond to individual progress and needs (Onyishi, 2024; Kamid et al., 2023). Through intelligent tutoring systems, adaptive learning platforms, and real-time analytics, AI-driven learning dynamically adjusts the problem difficulty, provides immediate hints, and tailors practice exercises to match each student's current skill level (Ni & Dai, 2025; Deckker & Sumanasekara, 2025). This personalization minimizes dissatisfaction and supports persistence by ensuring that the learning tasks remain challenging. Features such as progress tracking and instant feedback further encourage learners to continue engaging until they have mastered the subject matter.

Despite this agreement, doubts remain regarding whether persistence developed through AI support translates into independent capacity once technological assistance is withdrawn. Inconsistencies also surface, although some research contends that adaptive structuring promotes sustained persistence, others caution that it could result in a dependence on external support (Rosyada et al., 2024). These conflicts highlight the

necessity for a more thorough investigation into the possibilities of persistence supported by AI. Nonetheless, evidence suggests that AI-driven learning not only sustains persistence but also builds independent learning habits that are essential for long-term academic success (Hyasinth & Albina, 2024; Rosyada et al., 2024). AI-driven environments offer a particularly useful approach in mathematics, where sustained engagement is required for mastering complex concepts, through transforming persistence from a fixed personal trait into a skill developed through consistent exposure to adaptive, feedback-rich, and motivating learning experiences.

AI-driven Learning and Academic Performance

Academic performance in mathematics indicates how well students acquire, retain, and demonstrate their conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, and problem-solving skills. It is usually assessed through formal evaluations, such as examinations, assignments, and projects (Suleiman, 2023; Zheng & Mustapha, 2022; Chazan et al., 2021). In mathematics, high academic performance requires not only proficiency in analytical and numerical solution methods, but also the ability to model real-world phenomena and interpret solutions within their context (Gouia-Zarra & Gunn, 2024). Several factors affect students' performance in mathematics, including the quality of instruction, prior mathematical preparation, learning strategies, and availability of feedback (Attafuah et al., 2024; Tashoush et al., 2022). Many Nigerian universities continue to rely on lectures, which limits opportunities for deep learning by restricting active engagement, using uniform timing, and delaying feedback (Balogun et al., 2018).

AI-driven learning tools such as ChatGPT, Photomath, Mathway, Gauth, DeepSeek, Symbolab, Microsoft Math Solver, and MathGPTPro, when combined with gamification elements like progress dashboards, performance badges, and adaptive challenges, have demonstrated the potential to enhance students' motivation and persistence, which in turn contribute directly to improved performance outcomes (Mohamed et al., 2022; Tashtoush et al., 2025). Their effectiveness is most evident when these tools are integrated with high-quality teaching practices that emphasize critical thinking, collaborative learning, and reflective problem-solving. Such a blended approach not only raises assessment performance but also equips students with transferable mathematical reasoning skills essential for advanced study and professional practice.

However, there is still divergent evidence regarding AI-driven learning and academic achievement. While several studies report positive outcomes, others argue that performance gains are highly dependent on the context, significantly benefiting students with strong digital literacy (Mustafa et al., 2024). Factors like erratic internet access and inadequate teacher preparation may restrict the effectiveness of AI interventions in areas with limited resources (Otikor, 2023). Furthermore, the lack of longitudinal research raises concerns about whether observed improvements in performance are maintained if AI support is reduced or withdrawn. These findings imply that while AI-driven learning has great potential to revolutionize mathematics education, its long-term success depends on equitable access, long-term integration, and strategic alignment with pedagogical approaches that go beyond short-

term performance to encourage long-term mathematical competence.

Methodology

A quasi-experiment with a pre- and post-test design was used in this study. This design was chosen because it enables the investigation of the impact of one (independent) variable on another (dependent) variable, such as the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on motivation, persistence, and academic performance.

The population of the study comprises all 200 undergraduate mathematics students in both federal and state-owned universities in Kano state, which were 193 students in the 2024/2025 academic session.

Two universities were randomly selected and assigned to experimental and control groups; this gives a total of one hundred and eight (108) students, that is, 56 students in the experimental group and 52 students in the control group.

The researchers administered the treatment; three AI tools—GauthAI, DeepSeek, and ChatGPT were utilised as instructional interventions. These tools were selected for their relevance to science-based courses, particularly Mathematics, their accessibility for students, and their ability to demonstrate personalised learning. ChatGPT and DeepSeek emphasise dialogue, inquiry, problem-solving, and reasoning, as supported by much research on these tools (Guler et al., 2024; Delima et al., 2024; Neha & Bhati, 2025). While GauthAI emphasises practice, reinforcement, and mastery, and provides an immediate solution rather than a chart. These chat boards are crucial for developing a deeper understanding and improving critical thinking skills in mathematics. They engage students in meaningful conversations and support learning and innovation.

Students accessed these tools via their smartphones, which were preferred over computers due to their accessibility. To promote equitable participation, a portable router capable of providing stable internet connectivity for up to 50 students was supplied in the classroom, particularly for those without personal internet data subscriptions. The experiment spanned ten weeks. During the first week, students completed a pre-test to gauge their initial motivation, persistence and academic performance levels. This was followed by eight weeks of intervention, during which students employed AI-driven learning platforms as part of their mathematics lessons. In the final week, a post-test was conducted to assess changes in motivation, persistence, and academic performance.

Three instruments were used for data collection: the Undergraduate Mathematics Persistence Scale (UMPS), Undergraduate Mathematics Motivation Scale (UMMS), and Mathematics Performance Test (MPT). The instruments were purposely developed for the study using the content of differential calculus. Thirty objective questions with options A-D were formulated in the MPT, while 15 items were developed for each of the UMPS and UMMS. The instruments were validated by five experts from different fields: mathematics education, mathematics, psychology, measurement, and evaluation.

The instruments were pilot tested to measure their reliability. Cronbach's reliability was used for the UMPS and UMMS, whereas the split-half method was used for the MPT. The reliability coefficients are 0.83, 0.86, and 0.78, respectively. Thus, the instruments are valid and reliable.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of AI-driven learning on the motivation of undergraduate mathematics students?

HO₁: AI-driven learning has no significant impact on the motivation of undergraduate mathematics students.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Undergraduate Students' Motivation in Mathematics.

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	Z	P	Effect Size (r)	Remark
Motivation Before Treatment (Pre-test)	56	3.49	0.11				Null hypothesis not accepted
Motivation After Treatment (Post-test)	56	3.98	0.23	-6.518	0.001	0.87	

Key: Effect size of 0.10- very small effect, 0.30 medium effect and 0.50 large effect.

Table 1 shows the results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test, which indicated a significant increase in students' motivation after treatment. The mean scores rose from 3.49 (SD = 0.11) before treatment to 3.98 (SD = 0.23). It shows that AI has impact on the undergraduate student's motivation having a mean difference of 0.49, as the research question asked.

The difference was statistically significant ($Z = -6.518, p < .001$) with large effect size ($r = .87$), demonstrating that AI had a positive

effect on students' motivation. The hypothesis stated "AI-driven learning has no significant impact on undergraduate mathematics students' motivation in Mathematics" is not supported, since $p < 0.05$.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of AI-driven learning on the persistence of undergraduate mathematics students?

HO₂: AI-driven learning has no significant impact on the persistence of undergraduate mathematics students.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Undergraduate Students' Persistence in Mathematics.

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	Z	P	Effect Size (r)	Remark
Persistence Before Treatment (Pre-test)	56	4.08	0.28				Null hypothesis not accepted
Persistence After Treatment (Post-test)	56	4.40	0.30	-6.524	0.001	0.87	

Key: Effect size of 0.10- very small effect, 0.30 medium effect and 0.50 large effect.

Table 2 presents the results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test, which indicated a significant increase in students' persistence after treatment. The Mean score increases from 4.08 (SD = 0.28) before treatment to 4.40 (SD = 0.30). Having a mean difference of 0.32 in favour of after treatment, indicated that AI

has impact on the undergraduate students' persistence. Thus, the research question answered.

The difference was statistically significant ($Z = -6.524, p < .001$) with large effect size of 0.87, demonstrating that AI had a positive effect on students' persistence. The hypothesis

stated “AI-driven learning has no significant effect on the persistence of undergraduate mathematics students in Mathematics” is not supported, since $p < 0.05$.

Research Question 3: Is there any difference in the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students between those using AI-

driven learning and those employing lecture methods?

HO3: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students between those taught using AI-driven learning and those employing lecture methods.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Independent t-test for the Impact of AI on Academic Performance.

Groups	N	\bar{x}	SD	M/Dff	df	t	P	Effect Size (r)	Remark
Control	52	71.81	6.12						Null
Experimental	56	80.44	5.91	8.63	106	7.455	0.001	1.44	Hypothesis not Accepted

Table 3 shows the mean, standard deviation, and independent t-test on the impact of AI-driven learning on the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students. The Table provides a mean of the control group of 71.81 with a standard deviation of 6.12, and a mean of the experimental group of 80.44 with a standard deviation of 5.91. The Table shows a mean difference of 8.63 in favour of the experimental group. This indicates that AI has an impact on undergraduate academic performance, thus answering the research question.

The Table also provides an independent t-test on the impact of AI-driven learning on the academic performance of undergraduate mathematics students. A significant difference was found between the academic performance of those exposed to AI and those exposed to the lecture method $t(106) = 7.455, p = 0.001$, with a very large effect size 1.44. The hypothesis stated, “there is no significant difference in academic performance between undergraduate mathematics students exposed to AI-driven learning and those using lecture methods,” is not supported, as $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

The results presented in this study demonstrate a significant increase in undergraduate mathematics students’ motivation, persistence, and academic performance after exposure to AI-driven learning environments. For motivation, the results presented in Table 1 revealed an increase from (M = 3.49, SD = 0.11) before treatment to (M = 3.98, SD = 0.23) after treatment, with $t = -6.518, p < 0.001$. This improvement is in line with the theoretical framework of Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2019), which emphasizes the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in sustaining motivation, as well as Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1997), which highlights the role of self-efficacy in guiding persistence and performance. AI-driven environments provided adaptive feedback, personalized problem-solving experiences, and gamified tasks that likely satisfied these needs, leading to improved intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. This finding supports earlier studies (Rizvi, 2023; Ryan & Vansteenkiste, 2023; Reeve, 2024) and aligns with Salleh et al. (2025), who noted that tools

like Photomath, Mathway, and Symbolab make abstract mathematical concepts more real and engaging.

Similarly, Table 2 reveals a significant improvement in persistence of undergraduate mathematics students, rising from ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.28$) before treatment to ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 0.30$) after treatment, with $t = -6.524$, $p < 0.001$. These findings support earlier research showing that learning is structured to reduce frustration while maintaining challenge, problem difficulty is modified in real time, and immediate guidance are given in interactive environments, which improve persistence (Daza-Pérez et al., 2024; Feng & Papi, 2020; Ni & Dai, 2025). Students were probably more likely to stay involved for longer due to this adaptive support, which supports DiNapoli's (2023) claim that persistence allows students to consider several possible solutions and develop a stronger conceptual understanding.

With respect to academic performance, Table 3 shows that students in the experimental group ($M = 80.44$, $SD = 5.91$) significantly outperformed those taught with lecture methods ($M = 71.81$, $SD = 6.12$), with $t = 7.455$, $p < 0.001$. This is in support with prior evidence (Tashtoush et al., 2025; Mohamed et al., 2022) who submitted that AI-driven platforms enhance learning outcomes by identifying knowledge gaps in real time, providing targeted feedback, and reinforcing conceptual and procedural fluency. It further supports Gouia-Zarra and Gunn (2024), who emphasized that AI-driven tools can make mathematical reasoning more practical and transferable when integrated with reflective teaching practices.

Although these results offer convincing evidence that AI-driven learning enhances motivation, and persistence and performance, it is important to recognize some potential

limitations. The study was restricted to two universities in Kano State, which limits the significance of the findings to other regions or institutions with different pedagogical, technological, or cultural contexts. Second, the intervention lasted only ten weeks, meaning the study cannot confirm whether the observed gains in motivation and persistence will be sustained over time. Third, motivation and persistence were assessed using self-report scales, which may be subject to bias. Finally, differences in students' digital literacy and access to reliable internet or devices may have influenced outcomes, raising questions about equity and access in resource-constrained contexts.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that AI-driven learning has a significant impact on undergraduate mathematics students' motivation, persistence, and academic performance. These studies have revealed that integrating AI technologies into mathematics teaching and learning could enhance learning outcomes.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Universities Mathematics lecturers should incorporate AI-driven learning tools into teaching to enhance motivation and persistence among students.
2. Regular training should be given to Mathematics lecturers for effective use of AI tools toward teaching Mathematics in classroom practice in order to maximize its benefits for academic performance.
3. The management of universities should adapt and regulate the ethical use and evaluation of AI-driven learning in the universities, as there is no other option

apart from accepting it in the educational sector, because the world has already embarked on the digital age.

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